

MAIN COMPONENTS AND COOPERATIVE RELATIONS OF PRESCHOOL PREPARATION FOR CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE

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Annotation: At this stage of the formation of the child's thinking, rather than meaningful components, developmental components should prevail. The services of the designers and pedagogues of the preschool educational institution should be aimed at directing each child to activities, analyzing the characteristics of objects and events, that is, distributing objects according to the indicated signs, distinguishing their differences and general characteristics. must

Key words: motivation, cooperation, preschool education, thinking, speech, educational psychology.

Introduction

Five key components of school readiness:

1. Motivational preparation.
2. Voluntary preparation.
3. Socio-psychological preparation for school.
4. Mental preparation.
5. Ability to read

How to prepare children for school?

1. To take care that the child goes to the preschool educational organization with all his heart.

2. Make demands taking into account age-appropriate norms and age characteristics of the child.

3. Try to make the child feel your love through actions and words.

4. Create conditions for him in the family.

5. Read fairy tales and poems, draw pictures. Talk to him as much as possible, discuss various topics. Regular monitoring of health and mood.

In conclusion, it should be noted that if the MTT, school, neighborhood, and family cooperation in preparing a child for school education is properly implemented, the quality and effectiveness of education and the goal set before us will be achieved. is important in implementation.

The cooperation work plan of the pre-school educational institution and the school will include the following. First of all, at the beginning of August, the psychologist of the preschool educational institution, the educator of the preparatory group, and the teachers of the primary school prepare and approve the plan of work with the children of the preparatory group of the preschool educational institution. Of course, the children of the preparatory group will be given information about school education, and work will be carried out to develop their imagination and skills about school. In September of the year, it is planned to

participate in the events of our independence anniversaries, the day of knowledge with children's performances, and to invite the principal of the cooperating school and elementary school teachers to these events and ensure their participation. Another of the events held throughout the year is the holiday morning dedicated to "October 1 Day of Teachers and Coaches". School teachers are definitely invited to this holiday. Through this event, they memorize poems dedicated to our teachers and coaches. By memorizing these poems, they will have an understanding of how our 19 teachers, who are no longer educators, teach them directly at school, and how much they should be respected and respected. Before being transferred to school education, children who are trained in preparatory groups in pre-school educational institutions must be examined by the psychologist of the pre-school educational institution. There should be a separate notebook for each child in the preparatory group, in which the child's test results and level of readiness for school education will be recorded. The results of such an examination must be mutually analyzed with a psychologist of a preschool educational institution, a primary school teacher, and a school psychologist. Of course, these works will be carried out gradually throughout the year. After the children of the preparatory group enter school, regular monitoring of the processes of getting used to the conditions there is carried out by preschool educational institutions and school psychologists. Of course, this process takes a special place in the adaptation of children to the conditions of school education

Story-role games and a dramatized center are a very comfortable environment for children to show their talents and skills. This center can also be called the center that forms the "I" of the child. All the equipment in the center is the equipment found in the children's life. During the game, the child learns to use them and has the opportunity to get acquainted with the professions. The game reflects the mutual relations of family members and provides an opportunity to receive moral education (and for the educator to study the family environment).

Experiments conducted at the Science and Nature Center on the experimental testing ground arouse interest in children and encourage them to make new inventions. This center is also the center of the greatest opportunity for children to learn about nature and its phenomena. If the activity of the center is organized correctly, children will learn 90% of the knowledge about nature. The center arouses interest not only in children but also in pedagogues. The information about where the things used in our life come from, what is obtained from them, the children sprinkled the seeds in pots with their own hands, put water in them and the seeds germinated.

The activity of the above-mentioned centers serves as a developing environment for preparing children for school education, and we considered it permissible to attach a map of school preparation for 6-7-year-old children. After all, the development map of a child of this age determines the success and efficiency of the educational process. For example, in a child,

1. Formation of physical development and healthy lifestyle
2. Socio-emotional development
3. Speech, communication, reading and writing skills
4. Learning (development through understanding)

5. Creative development is the main criteria that prepares him for the school environment.

After the end of the academic year, based on the monitoring of the preparatory group for the school, the comparison of the work done with the expected results is carried out, and through this, priority tasks of the MTT for the next academic year are determined.

The higher the quality and higher level of the educational process in the pre-school educational institution, the more easily our young people will acquire knowledge at the next stages of education. Therefore, we should respect the attention paid by our state to the educational process and use it effectively. On the basis of this, it is necessary to form the young generation as a well-rounded person and to raise them as necessary people for our country.

Preschool educational institutions are divided into the following types according to the direction of activity: Kindergarten, kindergarten, kindergarten, kindergarten at home (as an independent institution or a branch). Preschool and primary education institution (kindergarten). Pre-school educational institutions that educate students in one or more directions (language, artistic aesthetics, sports, etc.). Kindergarten of restorative type, which qualitatively improves deviations in physical and mental development of pupils. Kindergarten for the control and rehabilitation of weakened children, which implements medical hygiene, prevention and rehabilitation measures and procedures. Unified type of kindergarten (integrated type of kindergarten includes developmental, restorative and health groups in a generalized form). The working order of the preschool educational institution and the duration of the children's stay there were determined by the state requirements for the quality and level of preschool education, the charter, the agreement concluded between the preschool educational institution and parents, and the founders. Special pre-school educational institutions have been established for children with disabilities, and children are admitted to them based on the conclusion of the psychiatric and pedagogical commission established by the competent local education management and health authorities of the state.

Tasks of preschool educational institutions Every parent who sends their child to school believes that their child is ready for the educational process. Because everyone thinks that their child is capable and unrepeatably. But now a question arises. Is the child ready for school in all respects? Can he get used to new conditions? Successful preparation for school and adaptation to school life requires that this work be started earlier and carried out with patience, gradually harmonizing it with the interests of the child. The child's period from 3 to 6-7 years corresponds to the pre-school period. At this stage, the child discovers a new world for himself. Pre-school education is the initial part of continuous education. It ensures the formation of the child as a healthy and developed person, awakens his passion for learning and prepares him for systematic education. Preschool education up to 6-7 years old is carried out in state and non-state preschool educational institutions and in the family. The purpose of preschool education is to prepare children for studying at school, to make the child a healthy, developed, independent person, to reveal his abilities, to educate his passion for reading and systematic education.

In conclusion, it should be noted that working in children's development centers prepares them for school education, so that they grow up mentally and physically mature in all respects, and become loyal to national values and traditions. , increases their interest in the profession. The uniqueness of the Uzbek family lies in the survival of oriental manners, customs, traditions, national value and traditions, education, and the pursuit of spiritual

maturity. Family is the place that creates the main ground for children's education and learning.

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